

DEFORMATION AND FRACTURE OF ALUMINIUM - GRAPHITE
AND ALUMINIUM-ZIRCON PARTICULATE COMPOSITES

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Summary

Al-Graphite and Al-Zircon particulate composites have been prepared by liquid metallurgical techniques using Al-3% Mg as the base alloy. The wt % of the particulate phase has been varied between 10-30% for the Al-Zircon composite and 1.5 - 4.5% for the Al-Graphite composites. The particulate size investigated lay in the range of 75-250 μm . The particle size distribution, microstructure, tensile properties and the fracture toughness studies have been conducted in the composites to investigate the effect of wt % of the particulate phase and the particulate size on the strength, ductility, and fracture toughness of the cast composites as compared to the forged ones.

Introduction

Aluminium base cast particulate composites have recently been proposed (1-3) as the candidate materials for applications like cylinder liners, piston rings, pistons, bearings etc. where the properties such as light weight, wear resistance, seizure resistance, fatigue and fracture resistance etc. are required besides an optimum cost and the strength level. Some of the typical particulate phases used are mica, silica, zircon, silicon carbide, graphite, alumina etc. The Al-Zircon and Al-Graphite particulate composites represent the two extremes as regards the properties of the particulate phases are concerned. Zircon being a hard phase, the Al-Zircon composites provide wear resistance and abrasion resistance properties whereas the graphite is a soft phase and believed to possess good solid lubrication and the seizure resistance property (4). For the present investigation, therefore, the Al-Zircon and the Al-Graphite composites have been selected. These alloys are hopefully capable of replacing some commonly used copper, lead and tin base bearing alloys with considerable cost saving and improved performance.

Recently, researches have been reported on the wear resistance property and the tribological performances of the cast composites (4,5). The data is lacking on the behaviour of forged composites. Secondly, the increasing volume fraction of the particulate phases has been found to have detrimental effect on tensile strength and ductility (2-4). Also, a poor toughness may reduce the abrasive wear resistance of the composites significantly. The choice of an optimum volume fraction (or wt. fraction) of the particulate phase in the composite is therefore essential so that an improved wear resistance combined with a reasonable strength and toughness could be achieved. The present communication aims to investigate the effect of the wt. fraction of the particulate phases (Graphite, Zircon) as well as the particulate size on the strength, ductility, fracture toughness and the crack size factor of the cast and the forged composites. Attempts are made to determine the appropriate compositions in these composites having optimum combination of properties so that these could be commercially exploited after proper investigation of their wear and fatigue characteristics.

Experimental

Preparation of Composites

The commercially pure aluminium was melted in a graphite crucible using an electrical resistance furnace. The melt was heated to a temperature of 800°C and then degassed with nitrogen. The nitrogen gas initially was bubbled through concentrated sulphuric acid and anhydrous calcium chloride at a rate of 10 litres/minute. The slag was removed from the melt after degassing.

The Al-Graphite and Al-Zircon composites were prepared in this investigation by liquid metallurgical technique. Three particulate sizes were selected to study their effects on various properties in the composites. The size ranges used are 75-125 μm , 125-180 μm , and 180-250 μm . Particles smaller than 75 μm led to undue segregation and agglomeration during casting. Particles larger than 250 μm are not believed to have favourable effect on mechanical properties. For Al-Graphite composites, the weight % of

graphite lay in the range of 1.5 - 4.5 whereas for Al-Zircon composites, it was between 10-30%. The wt % of particulate phases were decided based on the previous experience with these composites.

The graphite powder is not miscible in pure aluminium because of their mutual non-wetting. Mg is believed to improve the wettability of graphite particles (6,7) and Zircon particles. The graphite particles being lighter, cause difficulty while being introduced into the melt. The addition of graphite into the melt was facilitated by creating a vortex in the melt (1-4). A mechanical stirrer was inserted into the melt and its speed was adjusted to 700-800 rpm to create the necessary vortex. The graphite particles were heated to 800°C and added into the melt through the vortex at a rate of 30gm/minute. The pieces of magnesium metal were also added into the melt along with the graphite powder and the melt was thoroughly stirred and subsequently degassed by passing nitrogen at a rate of 2-3 litres/minute. The molten metal was taken out of furnace hand stirred with graphite rod and poured into permanent cylindrical and rectangular iron moulds. The cylindrical castings of length 15cm and diameter 6cm and the square section castings of size $7\frac{1}{2} \times 7\frac{1}{2}$ cm and length 14cm were obtained. Care was taken to ensure uniform distribution of graphite particles in castings.

The Al-Zircon composites were also prepared using the above procedure. The problem of floatation was not encountered with zircon particles during their introduction into the melt.

The composition of matrix metal (Al-Mg alloy) and the composites (Al-Graphite and Al-Zircon) as well as the particulate sizes are reported in Table 1.

Table I. Composition and Particulate Sizes of Composites

<u>Matrix Comp.</u>		<u>Al-Graphite Composites</u>	
Al-3 wt % Mg.		Al-3 wt % Mg, 1.5% graphite	75-125 μ m 125-180 μ m 180-250 μ m
		Al-3 wt % Mg, 3.0% graphite	75-125 μ m
		Al-3 wt % Mg, 4.5% graphite	75-125 μ m
<u>Comp. of Zircon</u>		<u>Al-Zircon Composites</u>	
ZrO ₂ -	65.9%	Al-3 wt % Mg 10% Zircon	75-125 μ m
SiO ₂ -	32.2%		125-180 μ m
TiO ₂ -	0.3%		180-250 μ m
Fe ₂ O ₃ -	0.07%	Al-3 wt % Mg 15% Zircon	125-180 μ m
Vola-		Al-3 wt % Mg 20% Zircon	125-180 μ m
tiles -	1.53%	Al-3 wt % Mg 30% Zircon	125-180 μ m

Forging of Composites

The ends of the castings were removed and the castings were machined to eliminate defects like pores, cavities etc. The castings were soaked in a muffle furnace at 475°C for two hours. A 20% reduction was given by

upsetting forging using a 500 Ton Hydraulic Press to both the Al-Zircon and Al-Graphite composites. The forging direction coincided with the longitudinal axis of the castings. It was not possible to provide more than 20% reduction in case of Al-Zircon composite. The Al-Graphite composite was further soaked at the above temperature for 30 minutes and a 10% reduction in the length of casting was given.

Particle Size Analysis

The analysis of particulate sizes in the composites was conducted to determine the actual size distribution of the particles as well as to check whether any segregation and agglomeration of particles had taken place. Samples of sizes 2.5 x 1.5 cm were cut from different regions of the castings (from the longitudinal section as well as transverse section) and polished upto 600 grade emery paper followed by disc polishing with Al₂O₃ paste. The polished sections were examined under an optical microscope at 100 X magnification. Over 150-200 regions were viewed on the polished surfaces from each of the composites and photographed. The sizes of particles were measured using square grid eyepiece and the number of particles in each size range were determined. Over 400 particles were looked in each of the composites to ascertain the size distribution.

Metallographic Examination

The composite specimens were prepared for metallographic examinations by electropolishing the specimens using an electrolyte of methyl alcohol (2 parts) and nitric acid (1 part) to reveal the microstructure. The microstructures of cast as well as the forged specimens were studied for both the Al-Graphite and the Al-Zircon composites.

Tensile Test

Round tensile specimens of diameter 7.1mm and gauge length 28.3mm were machined from the forged as well as the cast composites with the longitudinal axis of castings parallel to the gauge length of the specimens. It may be noted that the direction of forging also lay along the gauge length of the tensile specimens. The tensile specimens were tested on a Hounsfield Tensometer using a crosshead speed of approximately 2mm/minute. At least five tensile specimens were tested in each case.

Fracture Toughness Test

Single Edge Notch (SEN) fracture toughness specimens (8) were machined from the forged blocks of composites with forging axis parallel to the longitudinal direction of the specimens. The specimen dimensions used were 10 x 20mm cross section and 80mm length. The dimensions were chosen based on BS 5762 (9) guidelines for the evaluation of crack tip opening displacement (CTOD). A 'V' notch was provided on one of the edges of the specimens and the specimens were precracked using a Physmet FCM-300B Fatigue Precracker as per ASTM Standard (8). The specimens were loaded under three point bending and the crack mouth opening displacement (CMOD) was measured using clip gauge method. The CTOD and K_{IC} fracture toughness values were estimated from the load-CMOD diagrams as per the BS 5762 and the ASTM standards. At least, three specimens were tested in each case and an average value was obtained.

Results

Particle Size Distribution and Microstructure

Fig.1 shows the typical photographs of particulate phases from the polished sections. The zircon particles were found to be fairly spherical in shape whereas the graphite particles were somewhat deviated from the spherical shape. Nevertheless, for all practical purposes, they may be treated to be spherical. Fig.1 also exhibits some typical microstructures of the cast and the forged composites. Cast composites of Al-Zircon reveal dendritic structures whereas the Al-Graphite composites show somewhat finer and less developed dendrites. The forging led to the breakdown of dendrites in the Al-Zircon composites and resulted in finer matrix structure as may be seen from the figure.

Figure 1 - Typical microphotographs from Al-Graphite and Al-Zircon composites for revealing particle size and microstructure.

(a) and (b) - Al-Graphite, 1.5 wt % 75-125 μm and 125-180 μm .

(c) - Al-Zircon 30 wt % 125-180 μm .

(d) and (e) - Al-Graphite cast and the forged microstructure.

(f) - Al-Zircon cast microstructure.

(g) and (h) - Al-Zircon forged microstructure.

Fig.2 shows some typical histograms revealing particle size distribution in the above composites. The size range of most probable particles is reported in Table II. It may be seen from the table that the most probable particulate sizes in the composites are in fair agreement with the average particulate size used for composite preparation and constitute about 30% and

more of the total number of particles.

Figure 2 - Histograms showing particle size distribution in the composites.

Tensile Test Results

Some typical Load-Elongation diagrams for the composites of present investigation are shown in Fig.3. Both the types of composites show very limited plastic deformation preceding tensile fracture. The extent of plastic deformation becomes practically non existent in case of composites having higher wt % of the particulate phases (30% Zircon, 4.5% Graphite). The tensile properties for the cast and the forged composites are reported in

Tables III and IV respectively.

Table II. Statistical Distribution of Most Probable Particles

Composite type	Appropriate particulate sizes used. μm	Most probable particulate size \bar{D} μm	\bar{D}_{AV} μm	Number of most probable particulate size (%)
Al-Graphite				
1.5 wt %	75-125	90-110	100	40
3.0 wt %	75-125	110-130	120	31
4.5 wt %	75-125	100-120	110	35
1.5 wt %	125-180	130-150	140	33
1.5 wt %	180-250	210-230	220	28
Al-Zircon				
10 wt %	125-180	130-150	140	34
15 wt %	125-180	130-150	140	42
20 wt %	125-180	130-150	140	31
30 wt %	125-180	120-140	130	31
10 wt %	75-125	110-130	120	29
10 wt %	180-250	210-230	220	35

Figure 3. Typical Load-Elongation diagrams Al- 3% Mg alloy and the composites in forged condition.

Table III. Tensile Properties of Cast Composites

Aluminium-Zircon							
Particle size	Wt % of particles	Yield strength	Tensile strength	% RA	% Elong	True frac. stress	True frac. strain
μm		MPa	MPa			MPa	
125-180	10	68	77.5	5.5	5.5	82	0.057
	15	65	75.0	4.4	4.3	78	0.045
	20	63	73.0	3.7	3.7	76	0.038
	30	62	68.0	2.8	2.6	70	0.028

75-125		57	70.0	4.5	4.8	73.5	0.046
125-180	10	68	77.5	5.5	5.5	82.0	0.057
180-250		70	86.0	9.5	9.3	94.0	0.099

Aluminium-Graphite							
75-125	1.5	48	72.0	4.8	4.8	75.5	0.049
	3.0	42	52.0	4.7	4.8	54.5	0.048
	4.5	40	48.5	4.0	4.5	50.5	0.041

75-125		48	72.0	4.8	4.8	75.5	0.049
125-180	1.5	61	83.5	5.0	5.0	88.0	0.051
180-250		64	85.0	5.5	5.3	89.5	0.057

Fracture Toughness Test Results

From the tensile test results it was noticed that the forged composites demonstrated significant increase in yield strength and tensile strength in both, the Al-Graphite and the Al-Zircon composites. This was followed by a reasonable increase in ductility (as evidenced from true fracture strain and % elongation values). This was true for all the composites excepting the ones with higher wt % of particulate phases. The Fracture Toughness Test was therefore conducted in the forged composites only.

Typical Load-CMOD diagrams obtained during Fracture Toughness Test are reported in Fig.4. The initiation of maximum load point (as shown in the figure) on the Load-CMOD diagram was taken as the critical point for the evaluation of CTOD toughness value. The CTOD values were calculated using the relation (9),

$$CTOD = \frac{K_I^2}{2E \sigma_{ys}} + \frac{V_p}{1 + \frac{a_0 + z}{0.4(W - a_0)}}$$

where K_I is the stress intensity factor corresponding to the critical load, E is the Youngs modulus, σ_{ys} is the yield strength, V_p is the plastic component of CMOD, a_0 is the initial crack length, W is the width of specimen and z is the distance from specimen surface to the clip gauge attachment point. The validity of CTOD for the plane strain condition was checked

Table IV. Tensile Properties of Forged Composites

Aluminium - 3% Mg Alloy							
Yield strength MPa	Tensile strength MPa	% RA	% Elong.	True frac. stress MPa	True frac. strain		
83	165.5	48.5	38.5	229.5	0.663		
Aluminium - Zircon							
Particle size μm	wt % of particles	Yield strength MPa	Tensile strength MPa	% RA	% Elong.	True frac. stress MPa	True frac. strain
	10	78	100.0	9.7	9.7	110	0.102
	15	71	92.5	9.5	9.0	101	0.099
125-180	20	68	82.0	5.0	3.8	85	0.051
	30	41	41.0	1.9	2.1	42	0.019
75-125		67	80.5	5.0	5.0	84.5	0.051
125-180	10	78	100.0	9.7	9.7	110.0	0.102
180-250		87	112.0	10.0	9.9	123.0	0.113
Aluminium-Graphite							
	1.5	76	80	5.0	4.9	84	0.051
75-125	3.0	72	72	3.5	4.0	75	0.036
	4.5	44	44	2.5	2.5	45	0.025
75-125		76.0	80	5.0	4.9	84	0.051
125-180	1.5	81.5	95	6.0	5.2	100	0.062
180-250		84.0	100	6.2	5.5	106	0.064

using the relation,

$$B, a_0, (W - a) \gg 50 \text{ CTOD}$$

It was noticed that all the CTOD tests corresponded to the plane strain condition as per the above criterion. The CTOD values are reported in Table V.

The candidate K_{IC} (K_Q) toughness values are obtained from the CTOD toughness values using the relation,

$$K_{IC} = \sqrt{2E \sigma_{ys} \text{CTOD}}$$

and are reported in Table V.

Figure 4. Load-CMOD diagrams obtained during fracture toughness tests.

Table V. Fracture Toughness Results in Forged Composites

Aluminium - 3% Mg Alloy				
CTOD Value μm	K_{IC} (KQ) (MPa√m)	$[K_{IC}/\sigma_{ys}]^2$ (m)		
373.5	66.35	0.6654		
Aluminium-Zircon				
Particle size μm	wt % of particles	CTOD values μm	K_{IC} (KQ) (MPa√m)	$[K_{IC}/\sigma_{ys}]^2$ (m)
125-180	10	52.5	24.31	0.1008
	15	61.0	24.95	0.1293
	20	184.8	42.44	0.4067
	30	81.0	21.93	0.2950
75-125		53.8	22.82	0.1198
125-180	10	52.5	24.31	0.1008
180-250		51.0	25.33	0.0877

Table V. (contd.....)

Aluminium-Graphite

Particle size μm	wt % of particles	CTOD values μm	K_{IC} (K_Q) ($\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$)	$[K_{IC}/\sigma_{ys}]^2$ (m)
75-125	1.5	124.3	36.85	0.2448
	3.0	145.5	38.79	0.3022
	4.5	162.5	32.10	0.5542
75-125		124.3	36.85	0.2448
125-180	1.5	60.3	26.62	0.1100
180-250		55.0	25.81	0.0983

DiscussionEffect of Wt. Fraction of Particulate Phase on the Tensile Properties

Fig. 5 gives a comparison of the strength and ductility in the cast and the forged composites as a function of weight per cent of the particulate phases. With increase in weight % of zircon, the tensile strength and % elongation decrease drastically in the forged composites. However, the forged composites exhibit higher tensile strength and % elongation than the cast composites upto 20 wt % of zircon, beyond which the cast composites demonstrate superior strength and ductility. A somewhat different trend in the behaviour of tensile strength and % elongation may be noticed in the Al-Graphite composites as a function of wt % of graphite. The forged composites show an increased strength as compared to the cast composites over the entire region of composition investigated. On the other hand, the cast

Figure 5. Comparison of the strength and ductility for the cast and the forged composites.

(a) Al-Zircon

(b) Al-Graphite

Al-Graphite composites demonstrate superior ductility as compared to the forged composites.

In both the composites, the improved matrix structure in the forged alloy and the breakdown of coarse dendritic structure of casting is believed to enhance the strength properties. With increasing wt % of Zircon particulate, difficulty with forging was experienced which led to development of cracks in the brittle particulate phase and the matrix in the immediate vicinity. This has resulted in drastic reduction in strength and ductility in the higher wt % zircon composites. In case of Al-Graphite composites, no such difficulty was observed with forging (the graphite phase being very soft and deformable as compared to zircon). Therefore, the strength properties are by and large enhanced by forging. The reduced ductility in forged composites is believed mainly due to enhanced void growth rate caused by increased strain hardening.

Effect of Particulate Size

The effect of particulate size (the most probable size) on the tensile strength and ductility (% elongation) is shown in Fig.6 for a 10% zircon and 1.5% graphite composites in the forged condition. It is interesting to note that the tensile strength and ductility increase with the most probable particle size over the range of particulate size investigated (i.e. 75-250 µm). However, there appears to be a saturating effect of particulate size on the ductility of the composites as may be seen from Fig.6. With further increase in particulate sizes, a decrease in ductility would not be surprising. Thus, there appears to be an 'optimum size' of particulate phase which would

Figure 6. Variation of tensile strength and % elongation with the most probable particle size (forged condition)

provide an optimum combination of strength and ductility. Similar effect of particulate size on the strength and ductility of the cast composites may be seen from Table III.

It may, however, be noted that the wt % of particulate phase selected for studying the effect of particulate size happens to lie on the lower side of the range. With increasing wt % of particulate phase, the optimum particulate size which would provide an optimum combination of strength and ductility, may decrease.

Effect of Wt. Per Cent and Particulate Size on Fracture Toughness

It may be observed from Table V that in both the types of composites (Al-Graphite and Al-Zircon) the CTOD toughness increases with the wt % of the particulate phase, however, in Al-Zircon composite, the CTOD has a tendency to decrease at higher wt % of Zircon. The K_{IC} fracture toughness (as derived from CTOD) reflects more prominently the decreasing tendency of toughness with higher wt % of particulate phases in both, the Al-Zircon and the Al-Graphite composites. The effect of tensile strength on the fracture toughness of composites for a given size of particulate phase is presented in Fig.7. For Al-Zircon composites, the tensile strength of 80 MPa appears to possess the maximum toughness. Beyond this, the increasing tensile strength has a tendency to reduce the fracture toughness. In Al-Graphite composites, the optimum toughness appears to be associated

Figure 7. The effect of tensile strength on the fracture toughness of composites for a given particle size.

with a tensile strength of about 70 MPa.

Table V also provides some interesting information on the effect of particulate size (for a given wt %) on the fracture toughness values of the composites. The fracture toughness remains insensitive to particulate size in Al-Zircon composites inspite of the fact that there is a significant increase in tensile strength (from 80.5 to 112 MPa). Thus, even somewhat coarser particles of Zircon do not appear to have detrimental effect on fracture toughness. In case of Al-Graphite composites, the fracture toughness is found to decrease considerably (from 124 μm to 55 μm in CTOD and from 36.85 to 25.81 MPa√m in K_{IC}) with the increase in most probable particulate size from 100 μm to 220 μm. Thus, the coarser particles of graphite are not

really favourable from toughness point of view.

Comparison between the Al-Zircon and the Al-Graphite Composites

A comparison of the above two composites maybe made in the regime of wt % used in the present work. Evidently (See Table IV) the Al-Zircon composites provide higher tensile strength and ductility (as measured by % elongation) as compared to the Al-Graphite composites. However, a more appropriate comparison of their fracture toughness can be made by calculating the 'crack size factor' which gives the crack size tolerance of the composite. The crack size factor is expressed by $(K_{Ic}/\sigma_{ys})^2$. Fig.8 represents the variation of crack size factor with the wt % of particulate phases. It is interesting to note that the crack size factor increases with wt % in Al-Graphite composites and attains higher values than the Al-Zircon ones. In the Al-Zircon composites the maximum value of crack size factor is obtained for a 20 wt % Zircon composite which possesses a tensile strength of 82 MPa. This appears to be the optimum composition in Al-Zircon composite to provide an optimum combination of strength and fracture toughness.

Figure 8. Variation of crack size factor with the wt % of particulate phase.

Conclusions

1. Forged Al-Zircon and Al-Graphite composites are found to generally possess superior strength and ductility as compared to the cast composites upto a 20 wt % and 3 wt % of the particulate phases respectively.
2. With increasing wt % of the particulate phase, the strength properties (yield strength tensile strength) and ductility (% elongation, true fracture strain) have a tendency to decrease in the Al-Zircon composite and the fracture toughness increase for smaller wt percentages. The 20 wt % Zircon composite with about 80 MPa tensile strength is found to possess the maximum fracture toughness value ($K_{IC} = 42 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$).
3. The tensile strength and ductility decrease with the wt % of graphite in the Al-Graphite composites, however, the fracture toughness increases marginally with 3 wt % graphite composite which possesses an optimum combination of strength and toughness. When compared on the basis of crack size factor, the Al-Graphite composite demonstrates better crack tolerance than the Al-Zircon composite whereas the Al-Zircon composite exhibits better strength properties.
4. The increasing size of particulate phase has a beneficial effect on the strength and ductility of both the composites for the investigated range of 100-220 μm sizes. The fracture toughness remains insensitive to particulate size in Al-Zircon composite, however, it decreases significantly in Al-Graphite composite.

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